

CLIMAAX

climate ready regions

Deliverable Phase 2

Refined regional risk assessment including local data and comparison of results.

Extended multi-risks analysis for forecasting, monitoring, mitigation and adaptation strategies in Molise - CLIMoL

Italy, Molise

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Leading Institution	Molise Region
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Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
CLIMol	Extended multi-risks analysis for forecasting, monitoring, mitigation and adaptation strategies in Molise (CLIMol)
CLIMAAX	CLIMAtE risk and vulnerability Assessment framework and toolboX
CRA	Climate Risk Assessment
ERA5	ECMWF Reanalysis 5th Generation Dataset
FWI	Fire Weather Index
WUI	Wildland Urban Interface
D.L.	Legislative Decree (Italian legal reference)
RCP	Representative Concentration Pathway
EURO-CORDEX	Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment - European Domain
GCM	General Circulation Model
CAE	CAE S.p.A
RCM	Regional Climate Model

Executive summary

This deliverable presents the outcomes of Phase 2 of the CLIMol Project, implemented within the CLIMAAX initiative for the Molise Region, Italy. The report addresses the need to assess climate risks systematically in order to support evidence-based decision-making and strengthen the resilience of the regional territory in the context of climate change.

The document provides an in-depth assessment of the main climate-related hazards affecting Molise, namely heavy rainfall over 3-hour and 24-hour accumulation periods and wildfires, using datasets with high spatial resolution.

The objective of Phase 2 is to analyse locally derived data on accumulated rainfall over 3-hour and 24-hour periods, together with the Canadian Fire Weather Index (FWI), used as a forecasting indicator of wildfire behaviour.

This analysis is intended to provide a higher level of detail for each individual risk, thereby enabling a more accurate territorial assessment and the definition of more effective mitigation and adaptation strategies.

For the heavy rainfall assessment, two datasets were used: observations collected from meteorological stations distributed across the Molise Region (the Regional Meteorological Network dataset) and a dataset derived from ERA5 downscaling at approximately 3 km resolution and subsequently reprojected (the CHAPTER/RISICO dataset).

This approach was necessary because the initial analysis already highlighted limitations in the spatial and temporal coverage of local data. The meteorological stations were installed progressively and unevenly across the regional territory, and therefore do not yet provide a continuous thirty-year record or complete regional coverage.

The use of these data was also enabled by the algorithm made available within the CLIMAAX Toolbox, which was applied to both datasets.

The results obtained are presented in the dedicated sections of this report.

A slightly different approach was adopted for the FWI analysis. A regional-scale FWI run was performed using the CHAPTER/RISICO dataset and the Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) model.

The downscaling process provides more detailed information for the variables of interest. The run covers the period 1981-2022. In this case as well, the model made available through the CLIMAAX Toolbox was used to perform the same analyses carried out during Phase 1.

Overall, the following key findings emerge.

Wildfires: future projections confirm the findings of the previous phase, indicating a general deterioration of meteorological conditions leading to very high FWI values and a likely increase in extreme wildfire behaviour.

Heavy rainfall: the situation remains less clearly defined, as future projections are not homogeneous. Running the algorithm on the two different datasets produces divergent results; the model applied

to the CHAPTER/RISICO dataset indicates more favourable future conditions than those derived from the Regional Meteorological Network dataset.

In conclusion, the analysis indicates that changes in meteorological regimes are already emerging, making the need for adaptation and mitigation increasingly concrete.

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

The Molise Region is located in south-central Italy, bordering Abruzzo, Lazio, Campania and Apulia. It has approximately 289,224 inhabitants, mainly concentrated in the larger urban centres of Isernia and Campobasso, within a predominantly hilly and mountainous regional context. The topography becomes gentler towards the coastal area.

Molise consists of approximately 55.3% mountainous areas and 44.7% hilly areas. Its climate is semi-continental, with generally cold and snowy winters and hot, humid summers. In recent years, however, milder winters with limited snowfall and drier summers have increasingly been recorded. Rivers generally have a torrential regime, with flows that decrease almost completely during the summer. The region also includes several protected natural areas, including the Abruzzo, Lazio and Molise National Park, characterised by high-biodiversity forest ecosystems.

Social sector

The spatial distribution of the population follows the geomorphological configuration of the region. Larger towns are located in areas with gentler and flatter morphology, while the concentration of population in rural areas remains significant. Migration flows, particularly among younger generations moving towards larger urban centres, continue to be substantial and produce two major consequences: the abandonment of rural areas, with a consequent increase in forested surfaces, and the ageing of the population in those same areas.

Population ageing is not only the result of the migration of younger generations, but also of declining birth rates, leading to changes in the social and economic balance of the entire region.

Economic sector

The economy of the Molise Region is mainly based on agriculture, tourism and small-scale industry. These sectors, particularly agriculture and small-scale industry, are highly exposed to the effects of climate change, as climate-related impacts on the territory directly affect productive activities. Tourism, being more concentrated during the summer season and in coastal areas, is less affected outside peak holiday periods.

Other smaller but still relevant economic sectors include pastoralism and high-quality local craftsmanship, such as leather processing and textile production.

Structures and infrastructure sector

The Molise Region is connected to the rest of the country through high-traffic state roads. No motorway connects Campobasso or Termoli directly to other regional capitals. The distribution of the road network is necessarily shaped by the morphology of the territory: valleys provide the main transport corridors, but they are also among the most sensitive areas to exceptional events such as heavy rainfall and its effects.

1.2 Main objectives of the project

As indicated in the Molise Regional Adaptation Strategy, the primary objective of the regional administration is to improve climate risk assessment by adopting state-of-the-art scientific methods and the latest research findings. The use of the CLIMAAX Handbook framework supports the operational implementation of this objective. The multi-risk approach introduced by the CLIMol Project represents a significant step forward, improving the level of detail of vulnerability analyses, updating risk maps and integrating future scenario modelling into policy development. These analytical results are intended to support local authorities and communities in developing evidence-based adaptation plans and implementing targeted and relevant measures. Strengthening response capacity and regional resilience requires the use of locally structured analytical tools capable of supporting continuous climate risk monitoring systems. These infrastructure improvements are significant for the effective management of wildfires and hydrogeological risks.

During Phase 1, the project analysed future projections (2041-2070) of the effects of climate change on heavy rainfall (3-hour and 24-hour events) and wildfires, using the dataset provided by Copernicus. The results showed that the region is highly sensitive to climate change and its effects.

Phase 2 of the CLIMol Project aims to analyse higher spatial-resolution data in order to obtain a more detailed understanding of the future effects of climate change. The objectives of this second phase are:

- Identification of the areas most vulnerable to the risks analysed, including the elements of vulnerability and the ways in which these risks threaten the territory and the population.
- Definition of an initial framework for identifying areas to be protected on the basis of exposure to different risks.
- Assessment and analysis of the meteorological data collection system.

In summary, the main expected benefits of the project concern an in-depth analysis of risks related to heavy rainfall and wildfires, using standardised methods and new technological tools. The project also envisages the design and implementation of risk mitigation structures specifically conceived to address these climate-related threats.

1.3 Project team

The following actors participated in the project:

Tabella 1 - Project Team

Name	Description	Role in the project
Molise Region	Public authority with multiple responsibilities, including forestry and civil protection management.	Project beneficiary and coordinator. Main interlocutor with European institutions and CLIMAAX coordinators. Responsible for stakeholder engagement. Responsible for project communication and dissemination. Provider of selected analytical data.

Beta 80	A company specialized in the management of big data.	Provider of highly specialised technical staff for data management and algorithm execution.
D.R.E.Am Italia	Forestry cooperative specialised in environmental engineering and wildfire prevention.	Provider of technical experts in wildfire prevention and meteorology applied to civil protection.

1.4 Outline of the document's structure

The document is structured as follows. The first part (Chapter 1) introduces the second phase of the CLIMol Project, recalling several aspects already presented in the previous phase.

The second part, which constitutes the core of the project, presents the materials, methods and results used and achieved during implementation. Chapter 2 is divided into several subsections, each of which addresses the two risks analysed in the CLIMol Project in parallel: wildfires and heavy rainfall.

The third part (Chapter 3) presents the conclusions, briefly summarising the results and discussing their validity and significance.

2 Climate risk assessment – phase 2

The scoping phase is necessary to define the steps following Phase 1. After the execution, in Phase 1, of the algorithm made available by the CLIMAAX project through the Toolbox, it is now necessary, before planning practical actions for mitigating the analysed risks, to validate and adapt the results to the local context using data with higher spatial resolution.

2.1 Scoping

The second deliverable of the CLIMol Project is developed within a context that remains broadly unchanged compared with Phase 1. The objective remains the definition of future projections for risks associated with heavy rainfall and wildfires, but with a higher spatial resolution.

The implementation of this second phase encountered limitations in the availability of locally sourced data, as the meteorological stations were installed progressively over time, starting in the 1990s. This resulted in two main issues:

1. The temporal resolution of the data is not sufficient to ensure statistical validity, and the various stations were installed in different years.
2. The spatial resolution of the network does not cover the entire regional territory, as the installation of new stations is still ongoing.

2.1.1 Objectives

The main objective of the Climate Risk Assessment (CRA) during Phase 2 of the CLIMol Project is to continue the work initiated in Phase 1, namely to provide a clear understanding, based on two different datasets, of the two climate hazards most relevant to the Molise Region: heavy rainfall and wildfires. This is achieved using the methodology and tools provided by the CLIMAAX Climate Risk Assessment framework, with the aim of providing an operational instrument for policy and management processes focused on multi-risk mitigation. Specifically, CLIMol aims, on the one hand, to produce a set of maps, including risk maps, to be used as a basis for Phase 3 of the project and for the design of small, targeted and effective interventions; and, on the other hand, to identify additional effective actions to mitigate the risks analysed.

The specific characteristics of the envisaged interventions - small, targeted and effective - derive from the urgent need to protect the population and the cultural and natural heritage of the region, as well as from the lack of adequate resources to manage the entire regional territory properly. Another objective is the planning of future maintenance interventions, so that the efforts and resources invested during the design phase can generate medium- and long-term benefits.

The main limitations at this stage are the following:

- Availability of a sufficiently extensive dataset, both spatially and temporally, to ensure statistical and practical validity.
- Involvement of additional stakeholders and, above all, the population.
- Applicability of the data used as a basis for mapping future interventions.

2.1.2 Context

The Regional Civil Protection System is regulated by Legislative Decree No. 1 of 2 January 2018, which defines the responsibilities and tasks of both central government and individual regions. However, this law does not specify particular social and territorial planning procedures for addressing civil protection issues related to climate risks. Furthermore, the regions are fully responsible for wildfire prevention, forecasting and active firefighting. The regions have the authority to delegate these tasks to their Civil Protection or Forestry departments. In Molise, wildfire management falls under the jurisdiction of the Civil Protection Service for forecasting and active firefighting activities.

The CLIMol Project operates in a regional context where the Civil Protection Service supervises both wildfires and heavy rainfall events. However, while a document exists for wildfire management and planning based on national laws and guidelines (the Molise Regional Wildfire Operational Plan), the legal framework relating to heavy rainfall concerns only event forecasting and monitoring, and not the operational management of emergencies. This, combined with a regional context characterised by limited resources, has resulted in the absence of comprehensive risk planning or multi-risk strategies.

The political and institutional context favours an emergency-centred response to environmental crises, with prevention being addressed mainly through the training of operators at different levels.

There remains a strong belief that environmental emergencies should be managed through rapid response rather than prevention. However, this is not considered the most appropriate approach for effective multi-risk mitigation. Although operator training has recently gained greater importance, which is a positive development, it remains insufficient. A preventive approach based on robust data and scientific analyses, implemented locally through active land-management measures, appears to be the most effective solution; through CLIMol, Molise now has the opportunity to pursue this approach.

The sectors most vulnerable to extreme events are those that support the rural economy of the region, such as agriculture and pastoralism, together with the rural communities themselves. It should nevertheless be emphasised that almost the entire population is exposed to environmental risks, particularly those associated with heavy rainfall, owing to the topographical characteristics of the region.

The CLIMol Project aims to coordinate the management of different risks and develop a proactive approach to emergencies, with the essential support of the population and multiple stakeholders, including trade associations and local authorities.

Figure 1 - Wildfire risk map of the Molise Region. Source: Molise Regional Wildfire Operational Plan (Forestry Lab - University of Molise).

2.1.3 Participation and risk ownership

In this complex scenario, multiple actors are involved. The following stakeholder categories are therefore considered relevant:

- Trade associations
- Regional bodies and agencies
- Educational institutions
- Public institutions
- Media
- NGOs
- Research and training (Academia)
- Healthcare

2.1.4 Application of principles

The principle underpinning prevention measures, particularly those related to environmental risks, is that all actors belonging to a territory should be involved. The territory is a space experienced directly

by all, although few are fully aware of this relationship. In this context, one of the objectives of CLIMol is to implement a communication campaign on the importance of active land use and management. To pursue this objective, additional stakeholders have necessarily been involved, including schools, environmental volunteer organisations and trade associations.

A second pillar of environmental prevention is risk analysis and the effectiveness of the actions that follow from it. This aspect, which will be further developed during Phase 3, is based on the need for all actors involved to agree on, share and implement the proposed actions, ensuring maximum transparency in their execution. Top-down interventions are considered economically inefficient and, in many cases, potentially harmful.

2.1.5 Stakeholder engagement

In line with the objectives of Deliverable 2, this section integrates a systematic stakeholder mapping exercise aimed at identifying all institutional and private actors that will be involved, in various capacities, in the subsequent consultation phases. This mapping is intended to structure future meetings for presenting the results and to support the co-design of adaptation strategies with key territorial actors. Direct engagement with these actors had not yet been formalised by the June 2026 deadline. This strategic and timing-related choice was determined by the need to concentrate available resources on a complex and priority research activity. Specifically, the work focused on the analytical assessment of the regional monitoring network and on the processing of environmental data. The activity centred on the reconstruction of historical precipitation series, through the collection and normalisation of raw data recorded by meteorological monitoring stations distributed across the regional territory. The statistical analysis of these time series made it possible to map long-term rainfall trends, the evolution of rainfall regimes and the frequency of extreme meteorological and climate-related events at local scale. This empirical dataset required a considerable methodological effort in order to perform a rigorous comparison with the predictive outputs and risk models generated by the algorithms of the European CLIMAAX Climate Risk and Vulnerability Assessment framework. This calibration and scientific validation phase proved essential for verifying the consistency between algorithm-based estimates and ground observations, providing the technical basis required for the subsequent sharing of resilience policies with stakeholders.

To complete this methodological pathway, an official calendar of meetings with the mapped stakeholders will be defined in the coming weeks. This cycle of technical roundtables and territorial consultations will make it possible to transfer the scientific evidence emerging from the analysis, jointly validate the risk scenarios and define local adaptation strategy guidelines through a participatory process.

Tabella 2 - List of main stakeholders

CATEGORY	NAME	CONTACT
Water, energy, and transportation network utilities and infrastructure managers	MOLISE WATER SPECIAL AGENCY	protocollo@pec.moliseacqua.com
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Water, energy, and transportation network utilities and infrastructure managers	PROVINCE OF ISERNIA - ENVIRONMENT SECTOR	protocollo@pec.provincia.isernia.it
Water, energy, and transportation network utilities and infrastructure managers	PROVINCE OF ISERNIA - ROAD NETWORK SECTOR	protocollo@pec.provincia.isernia.it
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Water, energy, and transportation network utilities and infrastructure managers	PROVINCE OF CAMPOBASSO - ROAD NETWORK SECTOR	provincia.campobasso@legalmail.it
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2.2 Risk Exploration

As specified in the Phase 1 deliverable, the Molise Region is exposed to multiple environmental risks due to its geographical position and territorial structure. Its hilly and mountainous environment often favours intense synoptic precipitation events, which may also be associated with snowfall and very strong wind gusts. The morphology of the territory intercepts warm and humid air masses from the sea; as these air masses condense, precipitation is released over the region. In recent years, this dynamic has been observed to intensify, mainly as a result of sea warming, which increases the energy available to thunderstorm systems [Cardillo et al., 2024; Cardillo et al., 2017; Cardillo et al., 2009].

Conversely, one of the drivers of sea warming is represented by heatwaves. Their regime has been observed to change both in terms of timing and duration [Cardillo et al., 2024; Cardillo et al., 2017; Cardillo et al., 2009]. This phenomenon produces thermal anomalies that have severe effects on fuel conditions, both dead and living, which in turn influence wildfire behaviour, making fires increasingly difficult to manage and more often beyond the suppression capacity of both ground and aerial resources.

The region is also exposed to other environmental risks, including heavy snowfall, floods and intense wind gusts, which may result from synoptic situations such as those described above. However, the events considered to have the greatest impact on the population and the territory - including crops, agro-forestry systems, structures and infrastructure - are heavy rainfall and wildfires.

2.2.2 Screen risks (selection of main hazards)

As specified in the previous chapter, the hazards considered in this deliverable are the same as those analysed during the previous phase (Phase 1). This document therefore continues the assessment of hazards and subsequent risks associated with 3-hour and 24-hour heavy rainfall and wildfires, using data with higher spatial resolution.

Wildfires

For the wildfire analysis, the Molise Region adopted its Wildfire Operational Plan, as required by national legislation. This document must be updated periodically with new statistics and relevant data. In summer 2025, the Molise Region updated the plan by producing a set of maps useful for the analysis of wildfire risk.

The first analysis consisted in subdividing the regional territory into five areas with uniform wildfire hazard, as shown in Figure 2-1. This subdivision was based on wildfire statistics from previous years, including number and extent of fires (Figure 2-2), and on vegetation characteristics.

Figure 2 - Wildfire hazard map for the Molise Region.

Figure 3 - Map of wildfire extent over the last five years.

The maps show a critical situation for wildfire risk. The hazard map indicates that the areas most sensitive to wildfire risk are the coastal and hilly areas, where the population is most concentrated during the summer season (lower hilly and coastal belt, eastern hilly belt and southern Apennine belt).

The revision of the maps has not yet included the wildfire risk map shown below; an update is therefore required, and CLIMol provides the opportunity to carry it out. In this case, risk mapping is not homogeneous, as many areas remain without an assigned value, especially in coastal zones where wildfire hazard is higher.

Figure 4 - Risk map included in the current Regional Wildfire Operational Plan.

Heavy rainfall

With regard to extreme precipitation, the available data are also alarming.

<https://protezionecivile.molise.it/rischio-meteo-idrogeologico/> According to the Regional Civil Protection System (<https://protezionecivile.molise.it/rischio-meteo-idrogeologico/>), recent years have seen a rapid intensification of events, with annual cumulative rainfall increasingly concentrated in a limited number of severe events.

Historical analyses for the period 1951-2007 show that extreme events, sometimes associated with other phenomena such as snowfall or strong winds, have had severe impacts on the population, infrastructure and crops. The exceptional events of 2003 and 2023 are cited as examples. The most recent severe event occurred in April 2026.

As expected, the statistical analysis produced a map estimating the spatial distribution of the average annual maximum 24-hour precipitation. This map shows that the areas most affected by heavy rainfall are located in the Apennine belt of the region, where the relationship between orography and meteorology plays a key role in precipitation dynamics.

Figure 5 - Qualitative map of the average maximum 24-hour precipitation accumulations.

The purpose of the map is not to quantify precipitation across the different areas of Molise, but rather to provide a qualitative indication of the areas most exposed to this type of phenomenon.

In conclusion, the selected risks are confirmed as highly impactful for the territory, including on the basis of the most recent updates. CLIMol aims to integrate these maps with cross-referenced information in order to identify the most appropriate strategic management areas.

2.2.3 Choose Scenario

As in the previous phase, the selected scenario for the FWI analysis is RCP2.6, while RCP8.5 was selected for extreme precipitation. Analyses were also carried out using the RCP2.6 and RCP4.5 projections.

Extreme precipitation

The operational protocol adopted for heavy rainfall follows the methodology applied to extreme precipitation. For the reasons explained in the previous paragraphs, annual rainfall peaks over 3-hour and 24-hour intervals were extracted through a downscaling process applied to the ERA5 dataset. Statistical distributions were then used to estimate expected maximum precipitation and

corresponding return periods, differentiated by duration and scenario. The analysis used EURO-CORDEX projections with a 12 km resolution, focusing on frequency and magnitude as key hazard indicators. The reference dataset covers the historical thirty-year period 1976-2005, while projections extend to 2041-2070 and integrate global (GCM) and regional (RCM) models with different greenhouse-gas concentration pathways (RCPs).

FWI

The workflow selected for wildfires was based on the FWI. This methodology enables the spatial and temporal evolution of the index to be monitored and seasonal variations to be analysed using data from the Copernicus Climate Data Store. RCP2.6 was selected as the main predictive scenario. Empirical evidence collected by local technicians, integrated with FWI model simulations, confirms that this threat is particularly critical for Molise. The risk affects not only ecosystem assets but also public safety, owing to the progressive expansion of wildland-urban interface (WUI) areas.

2.3 Regionalized Risk Analysis

Higher spatial-resolution data were used for the analysis of wildfire and heavy rainfall risk in the Molise Region. As specified above, the most precise data do not derive directly from a regional dataset, but from ERA5 downscaling, since local data are not yet sufficiently precise in either spatial or temporal terms. The following provides a brief comparison between the models used during Phase 1 and Phase 2:

- Phase 1: dataset derived from Copernicus CDS, with six EURO-CORDEX models, a temporal resolution of 1985-2004 and a spatial resolution of approximately 12.5 km. The model ensemble used simulates historical data; it does not consist of observations.
- Phase 2: the original data source is ERA5 (reanalysis of historical data from Copernicus CDS). A downscaling to approximately 2.2 km (EUR-02 resolution) was performed, producing the CHAPTER/RISICO dataset. The temporal resolution covers 1985-2004. The source dataset is derived from observed data.

It should therefore be emphasised that the difference between the two phases of the CLIMol Project concerns only the historical component, namely the input data used for the hazard analysis.

As a result, all findings relating to future projections and the risk analysis remain unchanged.

2.3.1 Hazard #1 (Wildfire) - fine-tuning to local context

<https://rdm.lab.lrz.de/records/0ppk7-znk14qui> The data used to run the CLIMAAX algorithm for the historical FWI analysis come from the CHAPTER/RISICO dataset (<https://rdm.lab.lrz.de/records/0ppk7-znk14>), which is an ERA5 downscaling product at approximately 2.2 km resolution obtained using the WRF meteorological forecasting model. The downscaling provides more detailed information for the variables that contribute to the FWI (previous-day precipitation, wind, humidity and temperature), covering the period 1981-2022. The CHAPTER data were reprojected onto the EURO-CORDEX grid to ensure compatibility with climate projection models. The historical period uses local observed data rather than simulations, providing a more accurate baseline.

Future projections were based on EURO-CORDEX models (Copernicus CDS), with EFFIS vulnerability data relating to vegetation, population and protected areas.

2.3.1.1 Hazard assessment

The wildfire hazard assessment is based on the processing of observed historical data, as specified in the previous chapter. Hazard refers to the probability that an event will occur in a given location and is therefore independent of the factors that determine the severity of the event. For this reason, a historical FWI analysis was performed using the procedure described above.

Figure 6 - Historical mean FWI derived from the CHAPTER/RISICO dataset. The figure shows that the highest historical FWI values are located in the coastal areas and in the Apennine belt of the region.

The seasonal FWI index represents the mean of the daily values recorded during the critical wildfire period, conventionally defined as June to September. This parameter is obtained by dividing the sum of the daily indices by the duration of the season. Within the CLIMol project, two specific five-year periods were analysed: 2046-2050 and 2051-2055. With regard to emission pathways, the analysis focused on the RCP2.6 scenario, while RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 were retained as secondary variants. To increase statistical robustness, the multi-model ensemble mean was adopted. For the severity of estimates, the system allows the selection of best-case, worst-case or medium-case scenarios; in this analysis, the medium-case option was selected.

Figure 7 - Seasonal mean FWI under the RCP2.6 projection, corresponding to the medium-case projection.

Historical and projected maps make it possible to assess how climate change may influence the duration of wildfire-prone periods. The use of best-case, medium-case and worst-case scenarios identifies the range of possible variations. The extremes of this range are obtained by integrating the standard deviation, related to both inter-model and inter-annual variability, into the baseline value. Although the scenarios may appear widely separated because of differences among climate-model FWI estimates, this spread does not undermine the accuracy of the analysis. On the contrary, it represents the range within which future conditions in Molise may evolve, including both the most optimistic and the most extreme projections.

2.3.1.2 Risk assessment

The risk assessment, based on EURO-CORDEX future projection models, remains unchanged compared with the analysis carried out during Phase 1 of the project.

Figure 8 - Left column from top to bottom: burnable vegetation, seasonal FWI, protected areas and restoration cost. Right column from top to bottom: danger index, irreplaceability index, population density and wildland-urban interface

2.3.2 Hazard #2 (Heavy rainfall) - fine-tuning to local context

For the heavy rainfall hazard assessment, a dual-dataset approach was adopted, using both regionally sourced data collected from local meteorological stations and CHAPTER/RISICO data, according to the methodologies explained in the previous chapter.

The need to establish this comparison derives from the previously mentioned issue of station distribution and the length of the available records. To obtain results with both spatial and statistical relevance, the algorithm provided in the CLIMAAX Handbook was therefore run using this dual-dataset approach. This chapter presents the results obtained, and the comparison is made for hazard and risk outputs across the entire regional territory.

Future projections were based on EURO-CORDEX models from the Copernicus Climate Data Store, with a spatial resolution of 12 km and a projection period of 2041-2070.

Hazard assessment

The outputs relating to heavy-rainfall hazard refer to the cities of Campobasso, Isernia and Termoli. The charts below show the future projection of expected precipitation (left) and the probability distributions of the maximum precipitation series using the Generalised Extreme Value (GEV) distribution for each city (right).

Figure 9 - Left: annual maximum 3-hour precipitation projections (2041-2070) for Campobasso, Isernia and Termoli (from top to bottom). Right: corresponding GEV distributions. The CHAPTER/RISICO dataset was used for this analysis

Charts were also produced for expected 3-hour precipitation during the 2041-2070 thirty-year period, considering different return periods (1, 5, 10, 50 and 100 years) and the three projection scenarios (best-, worst- and mean-case), again using the CHAPTER/RISICO dataset.

Figure 10 - Expected precipitation for 3-hour events during 2041-2070 for Campobasso (top left), Isernia (top right) and Termoli (bottom), for return periods of 2, 5, 10, 50 and 100 years.

Finally, the results relating to the heavy-rainfall hazard are presented. In this case, the comparison is based on the outputs produced using the two different datasets.

Figure 11 - Mean 24-hour maximum precipitation for events with different return periods (2, 5, 10, 50, 100 and 500 years) under the future worst-case projection (RCP8.5) and the historical period. The figure was produced using the CHAPTER/RISICO dataset.

Figure 12 - Mean 24-hour maximum precipitation for events with different return periods (2, 5, 10, 50, 100 and 500 years) under the future worst-case projection (RCP8.5) and the historical period. The figure was produced using the Regional Meteorological Network

The comparison between the two graphs reveals a substantial difference: the CHAPTER/RISICO dataset is clearly the more optimistic. It shows that future projections for all precipitation events

with different return periods never exceed the historical values. This means that the projection indicates a general and uniform weakening of extreme precipitation for the return periods considered.

By contrast, the situation projected using the Regional Meteorological Network dataset is more complex. A substantial worsening emerges for precipitation events with return periods between approximately 10 and 250 years, whereas outside this range the historical projection remains higher (in mm) than the future projection.

Both models have limitations that must be considered. Although the CHAPTER/RISICO dataset is extensive in both spatial and temporal terms, it remains a projection based on a European-origin dataset, and this origin inevitably entails a degree of statistical uncertainty. Conversely, the Regional Meteorological Network model is based directly on the territory, making the data highly reliable; however, its spatial and temporal coverage is not yet sufficient to provide statistically significant projections.

In conclusion, the final graphs produced show the projected future variation, under RCP2.6, RCP4.5 and RCP8.5, in 24-hour precipitation with a 10-year return period.

Figure 13 - Projected 24-hour precipitation for the 2041-2070 period under the RCP2.6 scenario. The left panel is based on the CHAPTER/RISICO dataset, whereas the right panel is based on the Regional Meteorological Network dataset. The inset maps show, in both cases, the absolute (left) and relative (right) projected change.

Extreme precipitation for 2041-2070 under rcp45 climate projections.

Extreme precipitation for 2041-2070 under rcp45 climate projections.

Figure 14 - Projected 24-hour precipitation for the 2041-2070 period under the RCP4.5 scenario. The left panel is based on the CHAPTER/RISICO dataset, whereas the right panel is based on the Regional Meteorological Network dataset. The inset maps show, in both cases, the absolute (left) and relative (right) projected change.

Extreme precipitation for 2041-2070 under rcp85 climate projections.

Extreme precipitation for 2041-2070 under rcp85 climate projections.

Figure 15 - Projected 24-hour precipitation for the 2041-2070 period under the RCP8.5 scenario. The left panel is based on the CHAPTER/RISICO dataset, whereas the right panel is based on the Regional Meteorological Network dataset. The inset maps show, in both cases, the absolute (left) and relative (right) projected change.

In this case as well, the CHAPTER/RISICO model appears highly optimistic with regard to future projections: the magnitude of change is negative, or almost neutral, across the entire regional territory, whereas the Regional Meteorological Network model shows a localised worsening in the northern and western areas of the region.

2.3.2.1 Risk assessment

During this second phase, maps relating to heavy-rainfall risk for the region were also produced.

The following results were obtained using the two different models, CHAPTER/RISICO and the Regional Meteorological Network dataset.

Figure 16 - Change in frequency and magnitude of 100 mm/24 h threshold precipitation in the 2041-2070 projection using the CHAPTER/RISICO dataset (left) and the Regional Meteorological Network dataset (right).

The two sets of results are substantially different. A first analysis immediately highlights the issue of the different spatial extent of the two datasets: CHAPTER/RISICO covers the entire region because it is derived from ERA5 downscaling, whereas the local dataset covers the region only partially, since the meteorological stations do not provide homogeneous spatial or temporal coverage.

Another major difference between the two models concerns future projections. As already shown in the previous analysis, CHAPTER/RISICO provides very optimistic projections for the 100 mm/24 h precipitation threshold, indicating a decrease in this threshold precipitation across the whole region, suggesting less intense rainfall events and longer return periods. By contrast, the Regional Meteorological Network dataset suggests a localised worsening, namely an increase in magnitude and a decrease in return periods for precipitation events with the same threshold value over specific portions of the territory.

2.4 Key Risk Assessment Findings

As reported in the CLIMAAX Handbook, the assessment of the key risks addressed by this project is based on the analysis of three fundamental aspects: severity, urgency and the resilience capacity of the community in a broad sense.

Severity refers to the impact that a given phenomenon has on a territory, including both its natural and ecosystem components and its anthropic component. It therefore provides an indicator of potential economic damage to the environment.

Urgency refers to the temporal dimension of a hazard and therefore provides a quantitative indication of the ongoing change, in this case climate-related change.

Resilience capacity refers to all elements within a community that enable it to maintain its state despite an external disturbance.

2.4.1 Mode of engagement for participation

As explained in the previous chapters, the stakeholder engagement model will be applied at the beginning of Phase 3 of the CLIMol project. The feedback collected so far was reported during Phase 1 of the project.

2.4.2 Gather output from Risk Analysis step

FWI

For wildfire risk, the output used for the overall risk assessment is undoubtedly the future projection of FWI itself (RCP8.5, 2050 projection). This information is needed to understand where and how future projections indicate the development of heatwaves and droughts capable of driving FWI values towards increasingly high classes.

Precipitazioni estreme

For extreme precipitation, the risk output is, as shown above, twofold and not straightforward to interpret. Although the CHAPTER/RISICO results are more homogeneous, their projections describe a scenario that may not justify targeted regional interventions. Conversely, the Regional Meteorological Network dataset identifies specific areas where the projected change is more pronounced. These areas should therefore be assessed with particular attention during Phase 3.

2.4.3 Assess Severity

Severity represents the actual impact of a risk on the life of a community in a broad sense. In the CLIMol project, the aspects most susceptible to the severity of the analysed risks are linked to the social dimension, namely how a community and its components may respond to an environmental stressor.

Wildfire risk has historically had a strong impact on the population, since the period of highest risk (summer) coincides with the period of greatest influx, and the most susceptible area is also the most populated during the same period, namely the coastal area.

The risk of intense precipitation is relatively different. The severity of this phenomenon is broader both spatially, as it affects the entire regional territory, and temporally, as heavy precipitation can occur throughout the year. Its impacts are also more wide-ranging because intense rainfall can affect the population, infrastructure, agricultural areas and natural ecosystems.

For these reasons, the following values were assigned in the Key Risk Dashboard template:

SEVERITÀ		
	Attuale	Futura
Piogge intense	4	4
Incendi boschivi	3	4

3 - Substantial: High frequency and/or substantial impacts for the region or community with potentially intolerable, systemic effects; the functioning of communities, ecosystems, assets and infrastructure, the economy or the life and well-being of citizens is threatened.

4 - Critical: High frequency and/or severe impacts for the region/community with potentially intolerable outcomes; potentially systemic effects such as cascading impacts or risks; critical disruption of communities, ecosystems, assets and infrastructure, the economy or lifethreatening conditions for citizens.

2.4.4 Assess Urgency

Urgency introduces the chronological dimension into risk assessment, acting as an early-warning signal for the repercussions of the climate crisis. This factor establishes the timeliness required to implement the necessary containment measures.

Both threats analysed are expected to intensify, both in terms of event recurrence, including the cyclical occurrence of critical wildfire years, and in terms of magnitude, as discussed above. The worsening of these phenomena requires timely and well-structured responses.

Considering the nature of the phenomena addressed, a slow evolution is not expected; rather, sudden-onset events are likely, although they are partially predictable and capable of generating long-lasting effects. It is therefore plausible to anticipate an increasing need for planning and preparedness measures.

URGENZA	
Piogge intense	3
Incendi boschivi	3

3 - More action needed: Climate hazard and processes conditions are observed or projected to change significantly. They are anticipated to persist or happen during critical timing. If a future trend of hazard increase will be observed, the region/community is limited in taking action quickly. Adapting to the respective climate risk may take years to a decade.

2.4.5 Understand Resilience Capacity

Resilience capacity provides an indication of how effectively a population can return to a normal condition after an extreme climate event. This dimension is based on economic capacity and on human, natural, physical and social resources.

The Molise Region already has a number of strengths in place. First, it has a substantial legislative framework relating to Civil Protection, which analyses several risks in detail, including those addressed by this project.

The Region can also rely on human resources. Alongside the National Fire and Rescue Service, which is responsible for emergency management of environmental hazards, there is a Civil Protection volunteer corps with a wide range of local operational capacities.

However, other aspects of resilience are weaker. The economic and financial dimension is particularly critical for several reasons. The regional economy is based mainly on small-scale industry, micro-enterprises, agriculture and tourism, all of which are vulnerable to the impacts of climate-related hazards.

Finally, the natural capacity of ecosystems to regenerate themselves is undermined by the intensity and frequency with which certain events occur.

RESILIENZA	
Piogge intense	2
Incendi boschivi	3

2 - Medium: Medium resilience capacity or some CRM measures in place.

3 - Substantial: Substantial and broad resilience capacity with specific CRM measures in place, but space for improvement.

2.4.6 Decide on Risk Priority

The final assessment of risk priority is shown in the following figure, taken from the CLIMAAX Key Risk Dashboard template. After the analyses of current and future severity, urgency and resilience, the greatest risk for the Molise Region is identified as heavy rainfall, followed by wildfires.

With regard to severity, the impact of rainfall is considered greater because it often affects a much larger portion of the territory and therefore involves a larger number of people. Its effects are also more disruptive, as they can directly threaten the stability of a community.

With regard to resilience, beyond specific bulletins and protocols, the community has fewer resources and tools to address events of this magnitude than it has for wildfire emergencies.

2.5 Monitoring and Evaluation

The second phase of the CLIMol project clarified several aspects.

1. Regional Meteorological Network dataset: the dataset for meteorological variables managed by the Molise Region is not sufficiently extensive in spatial terms, while in temporal terms its extent is statistically valid only for some stations. Overall, the dataset can therefore be considered heterogeneous and should be progressively standardised, for example through the installation of additional meteorological stations. This implementation would allow increasingly precise data acquisition and, consequently, increasingly accurate analyses.
2. Priorities: thanks to the methodology made available in the CLIMAAX Handbook, it was possible to identify clearly which environmental risks require the greatest attention in the short term. The quantification of severity, urgency and resilience made it possible to establish a clear framework for the urgency of the analysed risks.

From a technical perspective, excellent cooperation emerged among the different stakeholders and specialised technicians. The retrieval of the necessary data, the execution of the algorithms and the analysis of results were made possible by the synergy among the various actors involved.

The information and dissemination activities addressed to the population were also of fundamental importance. They represented moments of training and awareness-raising on the environmental challenges that the Region is facing and will continue to face in the coming years.

2.6 Climatological-statistical characterisation of meteorological data from the Regional Civil Protection Meteorological Monitoring Network

ERA5The study of the main thermo-meteorological parameters, and in particular extreme precipitation, is currently based both on historical time series of in-situ measurements from a network of rain gauges and on reanalysis datasets, such as ERA5 data produced by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF). These datasets integrate various inputs, including ground-based measurement stations, radiosondes, polar and equatorial meteorological satellites and aircraft observations, which are then processed according to the laws of thermodynamic physics through advanced numerical weather prediction models, such as IFS. The dataset currently used for applied studies such as the present one can be defined as very high resolution, focused on land-surface variables and distributed on a regular grid of approximately 9 km, or $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$.

In this context, it is evident that the statistical analyses derived from the two different scientific approaches may produce even significant numerical differences. These differences arise from the following factors:

1 - Grid smoothing. A ground rain gauge measures the rainfall that falls at a specific point, whereas the simulation model calculates the mean accumulated value by spreading it over a square grid cell of approximately 9 km on each side.

From a climatological-statistical perspective, this generally results in an underestimation of precipitation outliers by the simulation model.

2 - Convective precipitation is poorly represented or simulated by the ERA5 mathematical model, because clouds with strong vertical development, which generate the most intense showers and cloudbursts, are generally much smaller than the computational grid. The model must therefore use mathematical approximations that do not always reproduce the actual point intensity of the precipitation event at ground level.

3 - Orographic effect. In mountainous areas, precipitation depends strongly on local morphological and morphometric characteristics, which can only be described through linear and radial measurements. In addition, even a very fine grid tends to underestimate the maximum elevation of reliefs, thereby also underestimating forced orographic uplift and, consequently, the precipitation accumulations generated by atmospheric disturbances.

The downscaling used clearly reduces these effects related to atmospheric thermodynamics and territorial morphology, but it does not completely eliminate the differences; therefore, the issue of discrepancies between the two output measures remains evident.

In the physical territory of Molise, strong oro-geographical complexity makes in-situ measurement, and indirectly also the modelling of intense pluviometric phenomena, a scientific problem that remains extremely complex. More specifically, since the precipitation timespans considered in this study range from impulsive 3-hour phenomena to orographic-synoptic phenomena of 6 to 24 hours, numerous factors contribute to the numerical differences between the two climate-analysis approaches used in the project. A common issue concerns air masses originating from the first and second quadrants (Adriatic Sea) or from the third and fourth quadrants (Tyrrhenian and Mediterranean Seas), which suddenly encounter the mountain barriers of the Matese and Meta massifs. Precipitation is alternately more abundant and concentrated on stau or windward slopes, namely the Adriatic side in the first case and the Tyrrhenian side in the second.

A study by Fazzini et al. shows that, in the Molise territory, precipitation accumulations with an orographic component account for more than 70% of annual totals.

With regard to convective precipitation, these events characterise the warm semester, between May and October, and their spatial distribution is strongly influenced by morphology, including the local overheating of internal basins. In this case as well, mathematical models tend to underestimate the associated local and intense precipitation phenomena.

That said, it should be noted that the modern monitoring network operating in the physical territory of the Molise Region and in its significant surroundings (Campanian Sannio, middle Volturno valley and Daunia) began in 1998, but in a highly irregular manner, following the gradual replacement of the former manually operated network managed by the discontinued National Technical Services.

Because of this interruption, most thermo-pluviometric time series available until the end of the twentieth century were definitively discontinued. Even by applying modern homogenisation techniques, it is not possible to recover fully homogeneous historical series, especially for data relating to intense precipitation. As is well known in the technical-scientific field, these events show a highly unpredictable spatial distribution, with very large differences in accumulated rainfall over extremely short distances.

A detailed examination of the temporal extent of the historical series shows that only 6 of the 52 monitoring stations currently in operation have data extending for approximately 30 years, that is, since 1998. Twenty-seven stations have records covering approximately the last twenty years, starting from 2007; although they do not meet WMO No. 1203 standards, they are overall suitable for a higher-level statistical analysis aimed at defining areas with homogeneous climate behaviour.

Given the considerable effort required to retrieve, validate and perform quality analysis on the data mentioned above, these important statistical investigations are still ongoing and their results will be presented in the Phase 3 deliverable of the project.

To quantify the mean climate signal, the available historical series, extending over approximately 20 years, were therefore examined preliminarily. This period is nevertheless sufficient to attempt a regional-scale climatological characterisation. This initial analysis, based on the annual maximum values of the timespans considered in the study and on their general trends, revealed a statistical distribution that will need to be scientifically confirmed through a dedicated cluster analysis. The preliminary results suggest a subdivision of the regional territory into four pluviometrically homogeneous areas:

- A - Coastal and low-hill belt
- B - Medium- and high-hill sub-Apennine belt
- C - Matese Massif area, likely also including the Meta Massif area
- D - Western Upper Molise and Volturno basin area

This subdivision of the territory differs slightly from that identified in the previously mentioned regional-scale study, which was based on less recent but much more numerous data and on monthly-scale meteorological parameters. The results of that study were later incorporated into the 2013 regional document entitled Hydrogeological and Pluviometric Study. That study identified five homogeneous areas, distinguishing the Upper Molise area from the Volturno basin area.

In this respect, the most critical issue lies in the fact that, throughout the upper and middle basin, there is no single homogeneous historical series with a record exceeding twenty years.

Through back-analysis, four measurement stations representative of the twenty-year signal were then identified among the longest available historical series:

- For Area A: Termoli
- For Area B: Campobasso
- For Area C: Roccamandolfi
- For Area D: Pietrabbondante
-

The graphical results of the trend analysis, together with the corresponding tendencies, are reported in Tables 1-4 and Figures 1-4 below.

Table 2-5. Area A - Termoli (75 m a.s.l.) - Table 1

Termoli	3h	6h	12h	24h
05/09/2001	29,6	42,4	62,6	64,4
29/08/2002	81,4	95,4	112,8	112,8
15/10/2003	55,8	70	88,6	89,2
14/11/2004	37,6	55,4	72,6	86,4
20/09/2005	35,2	42,4	54,6	63,8
27/08/2006	35	40,8	59,2	59,4
07/10/2007	26,4	30,8	36	43,2
15/11/2008	25,2	26,4	37,6	47,8
23/10/2009	48,4	62,2	65	87,4
10/09/2010	31	37	49,4	56,2
20/09/2011	83,6	92,2	98	107
13/09/2012	21,2	30	39,6	48,2
01/12/2013	25,2	40,2	69	91,2
04/10/2014	53,2	74	82,4	85,6
26/11/2015	24,8	38,8	59,2	88,8
15/07/2016	37,4	59,8	64,4	66,8
25/07/2017	22,4	36,4	57,8	85,2
26/08/2018	34	39,8	42,8	61
10/07/2019	41,4	45,8	46,6	46,6
20/11/2020	19,8	33,2	50,2	80,6
28/08/2021	29,8	30,4	39,6	48,8
25/09/2022	21,2	31,8	46,6	55,8
20/01/2023	33	46	57,2	68,4
09/09/2024	25,2	25,2	30	34,4
16/10/2025	40,6	47,8	78,4	91,2
average	36,7	47,0	60,0	70,8
Max	83,6	95,4	112,8	112,8

Table 2-6. Area B - Campobasso (751 m a.s.l.) - Table 2

Campobasso	3h	6h	12h	24h
13/11/2001	17,2	25,4	29,2	38,6
03/10/2002	12,7	12,7	12,7	12,7
18/06/2003	27,4	34,2	36,4	53
05/02/2004	20,1	20,1	40,2	40,2
03/10/2005	33,4	41,8	48	48,6
02/06/2006	18	22,2	39,8	47,6
10/06/2007	17,6	17,6	20	25,4
04/11/2008	37,4	45,2	45,4	45,4
27/06/2009	17,8	20	23,8	33,6
03/08/2010	27	36,2	47,8	59,6
15/08/2011	38,4	40	42,8	56,2
14/09/2012	19,2	30,2	32,2	53,6
29/09/2013	52,4	58,4	68,4	74,4
12/04/2014	41,4	46,6	46,8	49
14/10/2015	36,2	47	54,8	67,6
06/06/2016	28	32,6	33,6	46,2
02/09/2017	27,8	30,2	33,6	51,8
05/05/2018	31,4	32,4	38,4	48,4
24/08/2019	33,8	35,8	44,8	55,2
04/07/2020	32,8	35,8	48	56
08/12/2021	26,8	36,4	48	58,4
25/09/2022	26,6	44,4	66,6	70
07/06/2023	34,2	34,4	35,8	35,8
20/08/2024	34,4	37,6	37,6	37,8
23/04/2025	22,2	22,2	26,8	37
average	28,6	33,6	40,1	48,1
Max	52,4	58,4	68,4	74,4

Table 2-7. Area C - Roccamandolfi (851 m a.s.l.) - Table 3

Roccamandolfi	3h	6h	12h	24h
28/07/2001	43,4	45,4	51,8	67,4
22/09/2002	48,6	71,2	85,2	90,6
03/06/2003	59	78,6	97,6	108,8
14/11/2004	53,2	70	91	161
27/11/2005	30,6	53	93,8	127,4
15/09/2006	33,4	46,8	60	60
31/10/2007	35,4	45,6	57	77
05/12/2008	40	58,8	80,6	108,6
21/09/2009	42	60,2	93,6	96
08/01/2010	43,4	77,6	111,4	127
16/02/2011	43	64,6	101	118,8
24/07/2012	38,6	43,2	64,8	103
26/12/2013	51,6	83,6	119,8	135,2
09/02/2014	40,2	50,2	65,4	69,8
14/10/2015	71	87,4	94	116
05/03/2016	36,6	49	63	92,4
15/12/2017	62	91	127	147,2
28/10/2018	63,8	108,6	143,8	187
05/11/2019	66,2	101,8	140	152,8
27/09/2020	62,4	91,2	110,8	112
03/11/2021	59,4	74	126,2	166,2
09/08/2022	73,6	77	117,4	130,8
17/01/2023	52,6	81,8	114,4	147,6
28/08/2024	38,8	52,8	66,8	101
10/09/2025	79,6	84,6	103,6	130
average	50,7	69,9	95,2	117,3
Max	79,6	108,6	143,8	187

Table 2-8. Area D - Pietrabbondante (955 m a.s.l.) - Table 4

Pietrabbondante	3h	6h	12h	24h
27/08/2001	40	40	41,8	42,4
13/05/2002	32	38,6	38,8	55,8
20/10/2003	47,2	57,2	67	68,2
08/08/2004	43	43	48	48
16/11/2005	43	71,8	74,6	75,2
29/07/2006	55,8	57,8	57,8	57,8
31/10/2007	28,8	36,4	37,4	38,4
03/06/2008	32,2	34	45,4	68
21/06/2009	39,6	42,6	58,8	88,8
10/11/2010	33,8	43,8	46	68,8
30/06/2011	47	47,2	47,2	47,2
26/08/2012	34,4	34,6	34,6	49,6
20/08/2013	42,8	43,8	46,6	69
22/07/2014	35	42,6	50,2	67,2
14/10/2015	25,8	32,4	41,4	56
30/06/2016	57,8	68,6	68,6	81,2
10/09/2017	52,8	53,2	65,6	74,6
07/09/2018	36	44,4	62,2	76,6
19/12/2019	24,8	31,4	46,8	64,2
15/08/2020	39,4	39,4	56,4	71,4
24/08/2021	38,4	38,6	45,2	71,2
26/08/2022	36,6	36,6	36,6	41,2
28/03/2023	20,4	23,4	34,5	38
23/12/2024	15,8	17,8	21,6	22,4
25/04/2025	35,4	38,2	40,8	63,2
average	37,5	42,3	48,6	60,2
Max	57,8	71,8	74,6	88,8

In seeking to identify a relationship between extreme meteorological parameters and elevation, it is evident that no statistically significant relationship exists, with correlation coefficients close to zero for all examined time periods. Instead, the repeatedly mentioned effect of the orographic barrier formed by the Matese Massif is once again evident. However, as shown in the tables above, the coastal area records absolute precipitation values for short-duration events generated by deep convection that are even higher than those typical of the Matese area.

This confirms that, given the increasingly well-documented warming of the Mediterranean Sea surface, the land-sea-troposphere system has, at least throughout the warm semester and no longer only during July to September, very large quantities of latent heat available. In the presence of an unstable lower and middle troposphere, this can trigger short-lived but particularly intense phenomena. The ground-level effects of these events increasingly translate into high geo-hydrological risk conditions, including flooding in lowland urban areas, flash floods along the minor hydrographic network and gravitational slope movements in the clayey areas of the regional low- and medium-hill territory.

Figure 17 - Panels 1-4 show the recent climatological evolution of annual maximum precipitation for timespans from 3 to 24 hours, including the corresponding linear interpolation functions and equations.

Analysis of the outputs relating to the recent precipitation signal (Figures 1-4) reveals a non-homogeneous pattern. In the Sannio-Matese area, although the statistics are not significant, the trend appears to show a slight general increase for all timespans analysed, while the coastal sector and the Upper Molise-Upper Volturno basin area show a slightly negative trend.

This does not mean that absolute intense and abundant precipitation is increasing in the first area and decreasing in the second. Rather, a more detailed analysis of the graphs shows that recent precipitation outliers have occurred more frequently in recent decades in the first area and during the first decade of the current century in the second area.

This evidence suggests that extreme events may not be driven solely by the evident warming affecting the study area, but rather by mesoscale and local-scale factors that can determine the quantitative evolution of impulsive convective phenomena as opposed to advective phenomena.

The previously mentioned analysis of the last twenty years for all available historical series will be able to confirm or refute this preliminary signal.

In conclusion, the initial results of the statistical analysis of the available data reveal several limitations of the current meteorological monitoring network, which is excellently managed by the Civil Protection Service of the Molise Region:

- Lack of a significant number of homogeneous and continuous historical series on which to perform statistical analyses capable of comparing the results with those of ERA5 model outputs. In approximately twenty years, even without densification, the current network may be considered adequate for characterising the climatology of the physical territory of Molise.

With regard to the current spatial-altitudinal distribution of the operational network, the following actions are recommended:

- Implementation of dedicated sensors is strictly necessary in the Meta mountain area, where there is no monitoring station above 500 m a.s.l.
- Densification of the network in the Frentani Mountains area, especially along secondary watershed ridges, where orography plays a fundamental role in the distribution of summer orographic-convective phenomena and cold-season advective phenomena. In particular, stations are needed in the area between Agnone, Castiglione Messer Marino, Schiavi d'Abruzzo and Torrebruna, along the border with the Province of Chieti.
- Completion of sensor coverage in the coastal and low-hill area bordering the Province of Foggia, including the Larino-Campomarino-Ururi-San Martino in Pensilis area, which in recent years has been affected by flash floods of considerable magnitude. The same issue also affects the southern Sannio area and the Daunia area proper, again along the borders with the Provinces of Foggia and Benevento.

Densification of the snow-gauge network above 1,200 m a.s.l. is recommended, especially in relation to the possibility of flash floods in minor basins below the main regional reliefs and high-magnitude floods in the middle and lower valley segments of the main catchments, occurring during phases with abundant snowfall followed by advection of Mediterranean air, liquid precipitation up to high elevations and rapid ablation of the snowpack. This type of meteorological evolution at the regional Mediterranean-basin scale is occurring increasingly frequently in spring and, secondarily, in late autumn, not only along the Apennine chain but also in pre-Alpine areas.

2.7 Work Plan - Phase 3

The third and final phase of the project aims to implement interventions across the regional territory in order to mitigate the risks analysed during the first two phases.

With regard to rainfall, the analysis shows that the current spatial distribution of meteorological stations does not provide homogeneous data coverage, making the analysis more complex. One of the objectives of Phase 3 will therefore be to analyse the spatial distribution of these stations and to provide a more detailed assessment of the data presented in Section 2.6.

With regard to wildfires, the analysis confirms that mitigation interventions in the territory must be supported by an adequate organisational structure composed of people, expertise, technologies and procedures. In this respect, it is desirable that Phase 3 of the CLIMol Project, in cooperation with the Molise Regional Civil Protection System, should initiate the procedure for updating the Regional Wildfire Operational Plan, the document through which each Italian region regulates and organises its wildfire prevention and response system. This document is useful not only for establishing protocols, analyses and training pathways, but also for planning future activities, such as wildfire prevention works, improvement of access routes and implementation of infrastructure. The expansion of the meteorological station network is also useful for wildfire forecasting, as the monitoring of humidity, temperature, wind and precipitation provides accurate data for the indices and codes that make up the FWI.

3 Conclusions - Phase 2 Climate Risk Assessment

The CLIMol Project allows several conclusions to be drawn, which are presented below separately for each analysed risk.

Wildfires.

Molise is susceptible to wildfires because of several sensitivity factors, including ecosystems, urban settlements and economic activities. The analysis of this environmental risk made it possible to focus more clearly on forecasting-related issues, particularly the lack of a significant local dataset, and on territorial planning issues, since many tourism and accommodation areas are particularly exposed to this risk.

Heavy rainfall.

Although the results obtained are not fully consistent, it remains clear that the vulnerability and exposure of the region to this hazard are significant. One example is the precipitation event, partly involving snowfall, that affected Molise in April 2026 and temporarily interrupted road connections towards southern Italy.

Another aspect emerging from the analysis is the need to improve the Regional Meteorological Network dataset through the spatially homogeneous and comprehensive installation of additional meteorological stations.

4 Progress evaluation [1][2]

Tabella 3 - Overview key performance indicators

Key performance indicators	Progress
At least [2] workflows successfully applied on Deliverable 1	goal achieved
A minimum of [2] communication actions taken to share results with stakeholders (specific project sections also on www.regione.molise.it and www.protezionecivile.molise.it)	goal achieved
A minimum of [3] publications and dissemination actions (also using official social media pages (@pcmolise) while creating the hashtag #CLIMol for better spreading information)	goal achieved
[2] press conference	objective partially achieved (1 press conference held, second to be held)
A minimum of [2] articles in regional media mentioning the project	goal achieved
A minimum of [2] fully updated hazard maps of the applicant territory included in Deliverables 2	goal achieved
A minimum of [2] updated exposure maps of the applicant territory included in Deliverables 2	goal achieved
A minimum of [2] updated risk maps of the applicant territory included in Deliverables 2	goal achieved
A minimum of [7] different categories of stakeholders involved in the activities of the project	Objective partially achieved (stakeholder map completed, availability to participate in meetings acquired; meetings scheduled between July 2026 and September 2026)

Tabella 4 - Overview milestones

Milestones	Progress
CLIMAAX 1st workshop participation in Barcelona	goal achieved
Stakeholders mapping	goal achieved
Workflow 1 application	goal achieved
Workflow 2 application	goal achieved
Data collection	goal achieved
Risks scenario(s) refinement and improvement	Objective partially achieved (the inhomogeneity of the local network data does not allow the complete application of the CLIMAAX workflows, but we are very satisfied as it was an opportunity to enhance and analyse the data of our local network and hypothesize spatial distribution solutions for the new network to be proposed in the Phase 3 deliverable, at the end of the project)

<i>Milestones</i>	<i>Progress</i>
Evaluate impacts on RM plans	Objective partially achieved (the inhomogeneity of the local network data does not allow the complete application of the CLIMAAX workflows, but we are very satisfied as it was an opportunity to enhance and analyse the data of our local network and hypothesize spatial distribution solutions for the new network to be proposed in the Phase 3 deliverable, at the end of the project)
Stakeholders participation meetings	Stakeholders' availability to participate in project meetings has been obtained: meetings scheduled between July 2026 and September 2026
Stakeholders mitigation proposals integration	Activities to do
CLIMAAX 2nd workshop participation in Bruxelles	Activities to do

5 Supporting Documentation

- Main report
- Workflow:
 - Wildfire: FWI
 - Heavy rainfall

6 References

Cardillo, Di Florio, Valerio, Fazzini: Calculation of attitude matrices with forcing linked to meteorological and climate data and applications of artificial intelligence in data updating. 37th Annual Colloquium of the International Association of Climatology, 2024, Paris (France). DOI:10.13140/RG.2.2.23136.49927

Cardillo A., Fazzini M.: January 2017: exceptional snowfall in the central Apennines; case study of the Molise Region. Presented at the XXXI Annual Colloquium of the International Association of Climatology, Nice, France, July 2018 (under review) - Sciencesconf.org:aic2018:181727

Cardillo A., Di Pilla S., Fazzini M.: Statistical analysis of precipitation fields over 30 years on the Adriatic side of the Molise Region (central Italy): preliminary results. Proceedings of the XXIII Colloquium of the International Association of Climatology, 1-5 September 2009, Cluj-Napoca, Romania, pp. 109-114.